

Effect Of Methodpicture Mapping On Ability Write Student Explanation Texts Class VIII SMPIT Gema Insan Cendikia

Wawan¹⁾

¹⁾ Indraprasta PGRI University

Correspondence Email : wawanspdi842@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The Influence of the Picture Mapping Method on the Ability to Write Explanatory Text of Class VIII Smpit Gema Insan Intellectual Students. The aim of this research is to determine the effect of methodPicture Mapping on students' ability to write explanatory text. In this research, the researcher used a quantitative research method. The researcher chose a research design which was carried out with a pre-experimental research design (one group pretest posttest design). The sample in this research was 30 students. This research proves that there is an influence of method usePicture Mapping on the ability to write explanatory texts.

Keywords: Influence, Picture Mapping method, explanatory text

INTRODUCTION

Indonesian is one of the languages or communication tools used by Indonesian people. Indonesian itself is used as the National Language. In its position as a national language, Indonesian functions as a symbol of national pride, national identity, a medium of communication between citizens, between regions and between cultures, as well as a medium for unifying ethnicity, culture and language in Indonesia. In the world of education, Indonesian is a subject that has an important role in the intellectual, social and emotional development of students and is used as a basis and support for studying all subjects. By learning Indonesian, students can be expected to know themselves well, their own culture and the cultures of other people, express ideas and feelings, and participate actively in the society that uses the language, find and use the analytical and imaginative that is in him.

Indonesian language education is one of the important aspects that needs to be taught to students at school. From there, it is hoped that students will be able to master, understand and be able to implement language skills, such as reading, listening, writing and speaking. Indonesian language learning is directed at improving students' ability to communicate. This communication is of course in good and correct Indonesian, both verbally and in writing, and fosters appreciation for Indonesian literary works. In order to communicate well, someone needs to learn how to speak well and correctly. This method would be better if taught early and continuously.

Teaching Indonesian is essentially the process of teaching or teaching Indonesian language knowledge. Ilmu in Indonesian means studying all things contained in achieving Indonesian language goals. The main goal of teaching Indonesian is that students are able to communicate in Indonesian both orally and in writing. Orally means covering aspects of speaking and reading, while written means aspects of student writing.

Writing skills as one of the four language skills have a very vital role in human life (BSNP, 2006). In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the definition of writing is defined as: How to write is to make letters (numbers and so on) with a pen (pencil, chalk, etc.), children are learning, giving birth to thoughts or feelings (such as composing, writing letters). With writing skills, a person can communicate well, express good ideas and be able to enrich their experience.

Writing skills are important because they can be a means of developing oneself. This skill or intelligence can be characterized by a person's ability to use good language in speaking and writing. Writing

skills are one of the most difficult means of communicating. This is because by writing a person must use all the language skills that have been previously acquired and then that person must process the words they have to avoid misunderstandings.

Text-based Indonesian language learning provides space for students to develop various types of thinking structures because each text has a different thinking structure. However, not everyone has good writing skills because almost some people still experience difficulties in writing. In this case the text is explanatory text. Because explanatory text is a new text studied since the implementation of the 2013 curriculum so that students still have many difficulties in understanding and writing this text.

Understanding Picture

Picture is a two-dimensional visual media on a non-transparent plane, as stated by Rohani in Musfiqon (2012: 73), image media is media that is a reproduction of the original form in two dimensions in the form of a photo or painting. Images enable people to capture the ideas or information contained therein more clearly than those expressed by words.

Picture (image) is able to provide details in the form of an image as it is, so that students can easily remember it. Kustandi (2011: 45) explains "this media is a common language, and can be understood, enjoyed by everyone everywhere." Apart from that, Indriana (2011: 45) explains that "image media is also concrete, overcomes the limitations of observation, clarifies a problem presentation, is easy to obtain and can be used easily". Therefore, using image media will certainly help students in learning activities.

Understanding Mind Maps

A mind map is a strategy for maximizing the potential of the human mind by using the right brain and left brain simultaneously. This strategy was first introduced by Tony Buzan. Mind mapping is a way of placing information into the brain and recalling it at another opportunity.

Mind mapping is also called a mind map, the way it works is, arranging facts and thoughts into something similar map. So it will make it easier for us to remember information compared to using ordinary note-taking techniques. Mind maps are applied in the educational sector, such as engineering, schools, articles and taking exams. According to Sutanto (2016: 16) "Mind mapping is a graphic technique that allows us to explore all of our brain's abilities to think and learn."

The Nature of Picture Mapping

Picture mapping is a learning method that can be applied in the classroom. This Picturemapping method is a collaboration or combination of the use of Pictures (image media) and mind maps (mind maps). According to Sadiman (2003: 21) image media is an image related to subject matter which functions to convey messages from the teacher to students. This image media can help students to express the information contained in the problem so that the relationship between components in the problem can be seen more clearly. Image media is a two-dimensional visual presentation that utilizes image design as a means of considering everyday life, for example regarding people, events, objects and places.

According to Tony (in Huda, 2014: 307), "State that to make Picture Mapping" A person usually starts by writing the main idea in the middle of the page, and from there, he can spread it out in all directions to create a kind of diagram consisting of keywords, phrases, concepts, facts, and pictures."

The steps of the Picture mapping method according to Tony (in Huda, 2014: 310) are as follows;

- a. Shows networks and relationships between various points/ideas/keywords with the help of Picture stimuli (image media) are related to the learning material.
- b. Ask everything you already know about the topic.
- c. Plan the initial stages of idea mapping by visualizing all aspects of the topic being discussed.
- d. Organize ideas and information through Pictures (image media) by making them accessible on just one sheet.
- e. Stimulate thinking about creative solutions to problems related to topics related to Picture (image media).
- f. Review the lessons that have been learned from the information that is already known.
- g. Write an essay based on image stimuli.

The Truth of Writing

A person's skill in doing something is related to the power or ability he has and will provide benefits

for himself and others. As stated by Kundharu (2012: 103), writing skills are "the ability to express thoughts into written language through sentences that are structured completely, completely and clearly so that these thoughts can be communicated to the reader successfully."

A person's skills certainly vary, this can be seen based on the results they have achieved. As a teacher, he must know the potential of his students. This will certainly make it easier for teachers to direct the potential that students have so that it can be developed and processed so that it produces results and becomes a special skill that students have. According to Tarigan (2008: 1) "Skills related to language consist of four components, namely listening skills, speaking skills, reading skills and writing skills." These skills have a close relationship with each other. The relationship between these four language skills is said to be an inseparable unity.

Explanatory Text

Kosasih (2019: 114) believes that explanatory text is a text that explains a process of natural, social or cultural events. Natural events, for example floods and volcanoes, while social or cultural events, for example traditional ceremony processes. According to Priyatni (2014: 82), explanatory texts contain explanations about formation processes or activities related to natural, social, scientific and cultural phenomena. Explanatory text comes from the author's questions regarding 'why' and 'how' a phenomenon occurs. Explanatory text explains a problem from a question that arises as a result of a process of events that occur.

In explanatory texts, the process of something happening is the key to answering questions that arise about how the event happened. According to Mahsun (2014: 33), explanatory texts have the social function of explaining or analyzing or the occurrence of something. This means that explanatory text has the aim of explaining the process of an event occurring. This event is explained clearly in the explanation text. This is in line with Darmawati's opinion (2015: 76), explanatory text is a type of text that explains the relationship between logic and events. In order to be able to write explanatory text, the writer must know the ins and outs of explanatory text in more depth. Explanatory texts are often written to explain natural and social phenomena that occur around humans.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, the author conducted quantitative research using the pre-experimental design method, one group pretest-posttest type (single group initial test and final test). Arikunto (2010: 124) said that one group pretest-posttest design is a research activity that provides an initial test (pretest) before being given treatment, after being given treatment then giving a final test (posttest). After looking at this definition, it can be concluded that the results of the treatment can be known more accurately because it can be compared with the situation before the treatment was given. The use of this design is adapted to the objectives to be achieved, namely to determine students' reading abilities in learning to identify effective sentence elements in Explanation texts before and after being given treatment.

According to Riduwan (2011: 54) "Population is an object or subject that resides in an area and meets certain requirements relating to the research problem". The population in this study was class VIII students at SMPIT Gema Insan Scholar, totaling 60 students and registered in the 2021/2022 academic year. According to Sugiyono (2013: 118) a sample is "a portion of the number and characteristics possessed by the population." Meanwhile, according to Arikunto (2010: 131) a sample is "a portion or representative of a careful population." The sampling technique in this research is Simple random sampling proposed by Akdon (2005: 100) "Simple random sampling is a way of taking samples from members of the population at random without paying attention to the strata (levels) in members of that population." So in conclusion, random sampling is sampling without looking at random levels from the existing population by giving the same probability for each element in the population to have the opportunity to be selected as a sample.

With calculations to determine the sample size, the formula according to Surakhmad (Akdon, 2005: 107) is taken, namely "If the population size is less than 100, then the sample should be taken at least 50% of the population size. If the population size is equal to or more than 1000, the sample size is expected to be at least 15% of the population size." In this study, the population was 60 people, so it was less than 100, so the sample was taken at least 50%, namely 30 students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the average score compared to the pretest and posttest scores, namely 25. To obtain a standard deviation value of 7.878. To answer the problem formulation in this research, the t test is used as a test of the results of the research with the criteria that if the calculated t value is smaller than the t table value, it can be concluded that the research hypothesis is rejected, and if the results obtained by the calculated t value are greater than the t table then it can be concluded that the hypothesis research is accepted. For the t test results from this research, the calculated t value was 17.381. So based on t count $17.381 > t$ table 1.699 it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of using the picture mapping method on the ability to write explanatory text.

Table.1 T Test Results based on SPSS 22
Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 pretes - postes	-25.000	7.878	1.438	-27.942	-22.058	-17.381	29	.000

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis, it can be concluded that there is an influence of using the picture mapping method on the Picture Mapping method on the ability to write explanatory text for class VIII students at SMPITGema Insan Scholar Karawang.

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